

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF FORMULAIC EXPRESSIONS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: defining formulaic expressions is rather controversial and problematic because it encompasses a variety of theories and approaches such as idioms, collocation, proverbs, sayings, etc. For this reason, this paper presents a brief survey of the contrasting perspectives. It starts with earlier views of formulas focusing on the identification and definition of such phenomena and ends with a working definition for this research as an attempt to analyse this distinctive phenomenon.

Key words: Corpus, Formulaic Expressions, Applied Linguistic.

Finding a definition to formulaic expressions is not as easy as it appears because it encompasses a variety of theories and approaches. For this reason, this chapter presents a brief survey of the contrasting perspectives. It starts with earlier views of formulas focusing on the identification and definition of such phenomena and ends with a working definition for this research as an attempt to analyse this distinctive phenomenon. The next chapter builds on this by looking at the nature of the formulas themselves. Formulaic language expressions were mentioned as quite early as the eighteenth-century in linguistics literature. Before the middle of the twentieth century, formula had been presented as a well-defined field in the philosophy of language by Jespersen (1924) who claimed that every language has characteristic formulas. He described formulas as whole sentences or groups of words represented as units, which cannot be analyzed or decomposed in the way free combinations can. They may be regular or irregular. His analysis of formulaic language was of interest in that it provided various examples making convincing argument that part of its definition is that it cannot be changed. For example, a phrase like How do you do? is completely different from a phrase like I gave a boy a piece of cake. An Overall Study of Formulaic Expressions 25- The term 'prefabricated patterns' has been applied also to second language acquisition, particularly, by Hakuta who defines them as utterances in which segments of sentences operate in conjunction with a moveable component for example 'where's + slot for different insertion of a noun phrase or verb phrase'. Therefore, they are partly creative and partly memorized wholes.- Prefabricated routines and patterns were not seen by all researchers as effective and integral to language learning process. In an important article, Krashen and Scarcella concluded that routines and patterns play only a minor role in language acquisition and are fundamentally different from the 'creative construction process',

they distinguished the two by their relationship to language acquisition and their role in creative construction. The sorts of relationship they describe are as follows:- Prefabricated routines may develop into prefabricated patterns. That is learners.- depend on patterns and routines for communication- Prefabricated routines and prefabricated patterns may be realised by the processing.- of the language acquisition as creative constructions- Prefabricated routines and prefabricated patterns may be considered as ingredients- of the creative process.- However, these definitions are not wholly satisfactory as neither Brown nor Hakuta's definitions are sufficiently selective. If the definitions make a distinction from the surface structure and moveable components, we could consider all language elements and strings to share the same criteria (e.g. I gonna/will play football). There are not enough examples, forms, and types to be classified into the context of particular utterances. This is used to give whole utterances in a socially appropriate situation and the language is developed by learners who prefer to learn by 'feel'. She also suggests that there are individual differences among learners. Analytic style learners may have received clear caretaker speech, while the gestalt child may have received more rapid, conversational input. It takes a different view of formulaic language which he calls "automatic speech". He defines this a conventional greetings, overused and over learned expressions (such as be careful and first things first), pause fillers (such as you know and well), certain idioms, swearing, and other emotional language, which has been argued that it is located in both the right and left hemispheres of the brain. Evidently, patients who have suffered left hemisphere brain damage, (i.e. they have lost the ability to speak) could use automatic speech (for further reading. Van-Lanker has based his study on functionality in the discourse analysis from the psycholinguistic angle, introducing formulas as automatic speech by its relationship to certain idioms, (i.e. they are similarity based in convention-ality) and other emotional language. This, however, shows the weakness of automatic speech since it lacks distinctive-ness Moreover, Van- Lanker does not give the limited us-age of such expressions. For example, expressions like be careful and first things first can be used as imperatives and accordingly they could be considered as with other expressions, such as transitions, conjunctions, etc., as overused and over learned expressions. All in all, automatic speech has been defined as conventional greetings with means that it is con-fined particularly to expressions of greetings (e.g. hello, how are you?, how do you do, good morning, etc.) with no regard to other expressions of farewell (e.g. good-bye, see you, etc.), expressions of gratitude (e.g. thank you, I'm grateful, etc.), and expressions of apologies.

References:

1. Aijmer, K. (1996). Conversational routines in English: Convention and creativity. London: Longman. 30 IJALEL 8(3):24-30
2. Alexander, R.J. (1978). "Fixed expressions in English: a linguistic, psycholinguistic, sociolinguistic and didactic study". *Anglistik und Englishunterricht*, 6, 171-88.
3. Bolinger, D. (1976). 'Meaning and memory'. *Forum linguisticum*, 1, 1-14.
4. Brown, R. (1973). *A first language: The early stages*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
5. Carter, R. (1987). *Vocabulary*. London: Routledge.
6. Coulmas, F. (ed.) (1981). *Conversational routines: Explorations in standardized communication situations and prepatterned speech*. The Hague: Mouton.
7. Fernando, C. (1996). *Idioms and idiomaticity*. Oxford: OUP. Fillmore, C.J. (1976). 'Frame semantics and the nature of language'. *Annals of the New York academy of science*, 280: 20-31

